

Odour compounds in thermo-mechanically processed food based on pulse ingredients

SVENJA KRAUSE, Anahita Hashemi, Séverine Keller, Catherine Bonazzi and Barbara Rega

Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR SayFood, 91300 Massy, France
svenja.krause@agroparistech.fr

Abstract

This study investigates the effect of pulse flours (chickpea, lentil, lupin, yellow and green pea) on the formation of key volatiles with likely impact on the odour of sponge cakes compared to a wheat reference. Twenty molecules with an odour activity value of five or higher were determined from a wide variety of volatile compounds identified using headspace-solid phase microextraction/gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (HS-SPME/GC-MS) and quantified by internal isotope standards. While the majority of these originated from lipid oxidation, the remaining compounds were generated through Maillard reaction. Principle component analysis revealed that the lipoxidation-derived volatiles typically possessing green, fatty odours were mainly related to cakes made with lentil, chickpea, yellow and especially green pea flour. Among these, hexanal was assumed to be of substantial sensory importance based on its outstanding odour activity values. 3-Methylbutanal (malty, chocolate notes) was identified as most odour-active compound in all formulations and might have contributed to the overall flavour, in particular in wheat, green pea and yellow pea cakes. Moreover, lentil formulas were associated with 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine, which is known to be responsible for an earthy aroma. From these results it can be concluded that the raw material determines the potential to generate odour-active compounds during product development and mastering the reactions likely to occur might offer an opportunity to tailor the global flavour quality of food.

Keywords: lipid oxidation, Maillard reaction, odour activity, reactivity, cake

Introduction

The increasing interest for sustainable and plant-based eating practices has prompted the incorporation of pulses into the human diet. Owing to their high protein content and attractive nutritional value, pulses are emerging ingredients in baked goods, particularly in gluten-free or healthy food design applications. The substitution of traditional ingredients, such as wheat flour, by novel constituents might, however, alter the chemical reactivity during food processing due to a modified profile of nutrients with diverging susceptibilities to oxidative and thermal degradation. This can further be accompanied by the formation of volatile compounds, which in turn might affect the aroma quality of the final bakery products.

Therefore, this study aimed at identifying key volatile compounds with high probability to contribute to the aroma of sponge cakes made with different pulse flours (lentil, chickpea, lupin, green and yellow pea) in comparison to a wheat reference. Accordingly, the molecules identified using headspace-solid phase microextraction/gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (HS-SPME/GC-MS) and quantified by internal isotope standards were associated with their odour activity value and submitted to multivariate data analysis to estimate the potent odours in the different pulse-based applications.

Experimental

Sponge cake elaboration and characterization

Wheat and pulse cakes were elaborated as reported by Krause [1] from 45% (w/w) pasteurized liquid whole eggs, 25% (w/w) sucrose, 25% (w/w) wheat or pulse flour and 5% (w/w) sunflower oil. Twenty-one cakes were generated per cakes recipe, applying the three-step development process described by Cepeda-Vázquez [2], comprising (1) whipping of sugar and eggs, (2) addition of flour and oil and (3) batter baking at 170 °C for 25 min. In the pulse-based formulations, wheat flour (T55, Grands Moulins de Paris, France) was completely replaced by certified organic flours from lentils (Celnat, France), chickpeas (Celnat, France), lupins (Moulin Meckert-Diemer, France), green peas (Moulin Meckert-Diemer, France) and yellow peas (Improve, France). Immediately after baking, samples were deep-frozen at -20 °C in hermetically closed glass vessels until chemical analysis.

For each recipe, composite sampling was performed on ten cakes randomly chosen and ground in frozen state to a similar particle size distribution (d₅₀ ~250 μm). Reproducibility and repeatability of processing conditions were assessed at each step of cake development by means of classic physical and chemical measurements, including dry matter content, pH value, density and colour, as well as HS-SPME/GC-MS analysis [1].

Identification and quantification of volatile organic compounds

Gas chromatography (GC) analysis of volatile compounds was carried out as described by Krause [1]. Samples (2 g) were weighed in triplicates, spiked with 100 μ L aqueous solution of deuterated internal standards (411 mg/L hexanal-d₁₂, 15 mg/L furfural-d₄ and 3 mg/L 2-methylpyrazine-d₆), hermetically sealed in 20 mL headspace vials with PTFE-coated silicon septa and stored overnight at 4 °C.

Headspace Solid Phase Microextraction (HS-SPME) was performed by applying the following parameters: DVB/CAR/PDMS fibre (50/30 μ m, 2 cm, Supelco); incubation (18 min) and extraction (42 min) at 50 °C. Analyses were carried out using a TRACE GC Ultra gas chromatograph (Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with a ZB-wax capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.5 μ m). Compounds were thermally desorbed at 250 °C during 2 min and separated using the oven temperature program from 40 °C with an isotherm of 5 min to 240 °C at a rate of 4 °C/min. Helium carrier gas was used at a flow rate of 1.2 mL/min.

For detection, an ISQ single quadrupole mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was operated in the EI mode at 70 eV, scanning masses from m/z 33 to 300 and in SIM mode for selected molecules. Compounds were identified through mass spectra libraries search (NIST 08, Wiley 8) and by comparing their experimental retention indices obtained using a series of *n*-alkanes (C5-C21) with those from the NIST database. Hexanal, furfural and 2-methylpyrazine were quantified using their deuterated internal standards by isotopic dilution method. In addition, relative quantification of other specific classes of compounds was performed using 2-methylpyrazine-d₆ for nitrogenous-containing heterocycles, furfural-d₄ for furanic compounds and hexanal-d₁₂ for the remaining compounds (aldehydes, ketones, alcohols).

Determination of odour activity values

Odour activity values of the extracted compounds were determined as the ratio of compound concentration to its odour threshold in water described in literature. Nonetheless, sponge cakes are complex food systems, for which reason the utilization of odour threshold values in water can only give an idea of the most powerful odorants in cakes. Odour thresholds in matrices similar to cakes, such as starch, would give better insights into the odour activity values of individual compounds. However, this information is only available for a limited number of molecules in literature, for instance in simple starch models, which, however, are still far from the realistic cake matrix. Consequently, in order to take this uncertainty into account, only odour activity values ≥ 5 were considered for multivariate data analysis. Moreover, this value helped to select and hierarchize those compounds with probably the highest contribution to the odour of the final products.

Statistical analysis

One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) were performed on determined concentrations of volatile compounds and significant differences evaluated by Tukey's test at $p < 0.05$, using SAS studio version 3.8 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). Principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted on both concentration and odour activity values of extracted volatiles using XLSTAT version 2020.1 (Addinsoft, Paris, France).

Results and discussion

Complex profiles of volatile organic compounds were detected in the wheat and different pulse-based cakes, which mainly belonged to the chemical classes of alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, pyrazines and furans. In order to identify the compounds that are likely to affect the odour of the individual cakes, the odour activity values of all the 59 identified volatiles were calculated and those with an odour activity value of 5 or higher were selected.

As shown in Table 1, a total of 20 odour-active molecules was found with an odour activity value of 5 or higher. Among these, the majority of components were identified as typical markers of lipid oxidation, denoting the degradation of unsaturated fatty acids in the presence of oxygen, which can be either catalysed by endogenous lipoxygenase or triggered by heat, light and metals [3, 4]. In the case of sponge cakes, lipid oxidation is assumed to be initiated during batter beating, attributable to the entrapment of atmospheric oxygen while mixing the ingredients into a foam, and persists during baking due to heat-induced autoxidation [1, 5]. In the course of this reaction, hydrogen atoms are abstracted from the unsaturated fatty acids, thereby yielding hydroperoxides, which in turn can be converted into volatile compounds *via* subsequent reactions such as β -scission [6]. The odour-active molecules generated through such pathway and extracted from the diverse cakes were mainly deriving from linoleic acid (C18:2). Typical representatives included pentanal, hexanal, heptanal, octanal, 2-heptenal, 2-octenal and 2,4-decadienal as well as 1-octen-3-ol and 2-pentylfuran (Table 1) [6-8]. However, hexanal and 2-heptenal are likewise known as possible oxidation products of linolenic acid (C18:3), whereas heptanal and octanal could have alternatively originated from oleic acid (C18:1) [6, 7]. Both oleic and linolenic acid might have also been the precursors of the aldehydes nonanal and 2-hexenal, respectively [6, 7].

Apart from these lipoxidation markers, the remaining odour-active components were associated with the thermal-induced breakdown of sugars and amino acids mainly *via* Maillard reaction occurring during batter baking.

These included Strecker aldehydes (2-methylpropanal, 2-methylbutanal, 3-methylbutanal, acetaldehyde, phenylacetaldehyde), 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione and 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine (Table 1). Maillard reaction involves the condensation of amino acids and reducing sugars at elevated temperatures to produce aminoketoses (Amadori compounds) or aminoaldoses (Heyns compounds) [6]. In subsequent steps, these constituents are degraded through enolization, dehydration and hydrolysis into 1-deoxyosones or 3-deoxyosones [6]. Owing to their high reactivity, these α -dicarbonyl compounds are likely to undergo further reactions, resulting in the release of a wide variety of molecules. Among these, Strecker aldehydes are commonly found, deriving from the reaction of α -dicarbonyl compounds with amino acids [6]. In the present study, multiple Strecker aldehydes were identified as key odour-active compounds in the diverse cake formulations, comprising 2-methylpropanal, 2-methylbutanal, 3-methylbutanal, acetaldehyde and phenylacetaldehyde, which originated from valine, isoleucine, leucine, alanine and phenylalanine, respectively [6]. In addition to Strecker aldehydes, the nitrogen-containing compound 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine was present, being characterized by a very low odour threshold (Table 1). This heterocyclic molecule may have been formed from α -aminocarbonyls obtained next to the Strecker aldehydes in the condensation reaction of α -dicarbonyl compounds and amino acids. It is generally supposed that two α -aminocarbonyls react under formation of dihydropyrazine, which in turn can be substituted to create alkylpyrazines [9]. In this context, the generation pathway of 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine is postulated to involve the incorporation of acetaldehyde into the corresponding dihydropyrazine carbanion [10]. Acetaldehyde could not only emerge from Strecker degradation as previously discussed, but likewise from oxidation of ethanol [10], an alcohol that was largely present in the diverse batters and cakes (data not shown). Moreover, two further compounds with pronounced odour activity value were determined, namely 2,3-butanedione and 2,3-pentanedione (Table 1), which have been reported to likewise originate from Maillard reaction [11]. According to Yaylayan and Keyhani [11, 12], the former structure might be either directly formed from glucose upon dehydration and retroaldol cleavage or from the α -dicarbonyl compound 3-deoxyosone *via* pyruvaldehyde, followed by chain elongation by one carbon atom coming from amino acids like glycine. The latter pathway can be similarly applied to describe the production of 2,3-pentanedione, however requiring the incorporation of two carbon units into pyruvaldehyde, which, for instance, could be donated by alanine [11]. The authors further underlined that both structures could be considered precursors for Strecker degradation [13].

Table 1: Odour activity values, odour thresholds in water (OT) and odour descriptors of volatiles identified in sponge cakes made with wheat (WC), lupin (LUC), chickpea (CPC), green pea (GPC), lentil (LEC) or yellow pea flour (YPC). Only key compounds with odour activity values ≥ 5 are shown.

Compound	Odour activity value						OT [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Odour descriptor
	WC	LUC	CPC	GPC	LEC	YPC		
3-Methylbutanal	10264	8163	8963	10570	5802	11600	0.2 ^d	Malty, roasty, chocolate ^{a,b,g}
Hexanal	327	183	2641	5266	2675	3502	4.5 ^d	Green, grassy, tallow ^{a,b}
2,4-Decadienal			1174	1991	1209	1256	0.07 ^d	Deep fat fried ^b
2-Ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine	352	535	786	781	1207	869	0.04 ^d	Earthy ^b
2-Methylbutanal	557	468	606	652	353	742	3 ^d	Almond, malty ^b
2-Methylpropanal	108		523		271		1 ^f	Malty ^b
Pentanal	19	14	162	248	100	215	12 ^e	Pungent, strong acrid ^b
Nonanal	34	49	161	204	168	147	1 ^d	Citrus, soapy ^{a,b}
1-Octen-3-ol	15		132	289	142	179	1 ^d	Mushroom, vegetable ^{b,c}
Octanal	23	28	133	151	112	119	0.7 ^d	Citrus, flowery ^{a,b}
Heptanal	25	17	122	140	117	120	3 ^d	Green, fatty, rancid ^{a,c}
2-Octenal			33	72	33	43	3 ^d	Fatty, nutty, roasted ^b
2-Pentylfuran	10	5	57	36	48	38	6 ^d	Green, floral, fruity ^a
Phenylacetaldehyde	16	28					4 ^d	Honey-like, sweet ^{a,b}
2,3-Butanedione	27						3 ^d	Buttery, caramel ^{a,b}
2,3-Pentanedione	11	13	12	7	13	13	20 ^d	Buttery ^b
Acetaldehyde	8	8	10	17		14	15 ^e	Fruity ^b
Butanal			8	13	10	13	9 ^d	Malty ^b
2-Heptenal			5	13	5	6	13 ^d	Green, fatty ^b
2-Hexenal				5	5		17 ^d	Green, fatty ^b

^a from Birch [14].

^b from Pico [15].

^c from Murat [3].

^d from Buttery and Ling [16].

^e from Buttery [17].

^f from Belitz [6].

^g from Rega [18].

Figure 1: Biplots of (A) PC1 and PC2 and (B) PC2 and PC3 on odour-active compounds in sponge cakes made with wheat (WC), lupin (LUC), chickpea (CPC), green pea (GPC), lentil (LEC) or yellow pea flour (YPC).

The twenty odour-active compounds listed in Table 1 were subsequently subjected to principle component analysis in order to visualize how they drive the discrimination of the wheat and pulse cakes.

As depicted in Figure 1, PC1, PC2 and PC3 accounted for 63.61%, 19.54% and 8.72% of total variability. Along PC1, two groups of highly correlated cakes were distinguished. While wheat cakes (WC) and lupin cakes (LUC) clustered in the negative part of PC1, positive loadings were associated with cakes made from lentil (LEC), chickpea (CPC) green pea (GPC) and yellow pea (YPC). This differentiation was mainly driven by lipoxidation markers, which were characterized by positive signs, and thus, were directly linked to the second group of cakes. From these findings, it could be concluded that the unsaturated fatty acids contained in the associated flours possessed higher susceptibility towards oxidative degradation, hence promoting the generation of lipoxidation-derived volatiles. According to Krause [1], chickpea, lentil, yellow pea and green pea flours were not only significantly enriched in oleic, linoleic and linolenic acid compared to wheat and lupin, but concurrently comprised lipoxygenase with considerably higher activity, thus accelerating fatty acid oxidation. Following the general consensus of literature, the thereby released volatiles are typically responsible for a green, citrus and fatty odour (Table 1) [3, 14, 15]. Owing to its outstanding odour activity values among all lipoxidation markers identified, ranging from 183 to 5266, hexanal was assumed to be of substantial sensory importance. Interestingly, green pea cakes were characterized by the highest odour activity values of almost all lipoxidation markers. From this it was inferred that the associated green notes will probably be strongly perceived in this product. Lupin and wheat cakes, on the other hand, were correlated in the negative part of PC1 with phenylacetaldehyde, 2,3-butanedione and 2,3-pentanedione, probably emerging from Maillard reaction. These molecules are generally described to impart sweet, buttery and caramel-like odours [14, 15], however, they had only low odour activity values (7-28) (Table 1).

Further distinction of the individual cakes was obtained by consideration of PC2. As visible from both PC1 vs PC2 and PC3 vs PC2 biplots, the yellow and green pea products as well as the wheat cakes were spotted in the positive part of PC2, hence being associated with 3-methylbutanal, 2-methylbutanal and acetaldehyde formed during Strecker degradation (Figure 1). Of all odour-active compounds observed, 3-methylbutanal appeared to have the highest odour activity values in all products, varying from 5802 to 11600 (Table 1). This molecule is known to cause a malty, roasty and chocolate odour [14, 15, 18], which is likely to be easily perceived in the various cakes and could have been a key odorant especially in cakes made with wheat, yellow and green pea flours. In these products, the malty odour might have been intensified by 2-methylbutanal, although the correlated odour activity values were relatively lower. From the PC3 vs PC2 biplot, it further emerged that chickpea and lentil cakes were linked to 2-methylpropanal likewise reported to possess a malty but also almond-like aroma [15], however having similar odour activity values as 2-methylbutanal (Table 1). Consequently, it could be concluded that Strecker degradation was an important chemical reaction occurring in all products, yielding substances with similar flavour despite different amino acid precursors.

Lentil cakes further differed from the other cakes in the clear correlation with 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine (earthy notes) linked with negative loadings on PC2. Table 1 indicates a very low odour threshold for this heterocycle [15], for which reason it was supposed to be a strong contributor to the aroma especially of lentil cakes. Krause [1] assigned the higher ability of lentil flour to form pyrazines during sponge cake development to the exclusive presence of specific amino acids known to favour pyrazine production.

Interestingly, the discussed discrimination of the cakes based on the odour activities of relevant volatiles was comparable to that based on the concentrations of all extracted volatiles as reported by Krause [1]. This indicated that the selection of key odour-active compounds did not distort the global positioning of cakes on the PCA biplots and thus seemed to be an adequate approach to describe principle differences between the products.

In general, it needs to be considered that the overall odour of food is affected by a complex mixture of many odour-active compounds occurring at specific proportions. Consistently, the results presented in this study are primarily helping to understand and predict major differences between thermo-mechanically treated products prepared from diverse raw materials. Further techniques should thus be applied to gain deeper insight into the sensory discrimination of bakery products, such as cakes.

Conclusion

Total replacement of wheat by pulse flours seemed to considerably change the profile of volatile compounds with potent odour in sponge cakes. The volatile compounds were extracted from the individual bakery products by means of HS-SPME/GC-MS and quantified using isotopic dilution of internal standards. Odour activity values of all analysed components were determined on the basis of their calculated concentrations and known odour threshold values. Those molecules with an odour activity value greater than or equal to five were selected as main odour contributors and submitted to principle component analysis in order to evaluate their role in the discrimination of the diverse cakes. The majority of the twenty aroma-active compounds appeared to originate from the oxidative degradation of unsaturated fatty acids, while the remaining components were assigned to the thermally induced breakdown of sugars and amino acids mainly *via* Maillard reaction. This implied that different chemical reactions took place during sponge cake making, through which diverse compounds were released with interesting odour characteristics.

Multivariate data analysis disclosed that the pulse-based cakes mainly differed from the wheat cakes in being strongly correlated with lipoxidation markers usually possessing green, fatty odours. Among these pulse products, lupin represented an exception as it was rather related to Maillard-derived compounds with known buttery, sweet notes, which were concurrently associated with the wheat cakes. Nonetheless, Maillard reaction also seemed to play a non-negligible role in the pulse-containing products. In the course of this reaction, Strecker aldehydes seemed to be released with probable sensory importance (typically malty odours) in all samples examined, particularly in wheat, yellow pea and green pea cakes. In addition, lentil cake could be further discriminated by its association with 2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine, which was suggested to be responsible for an earthy aroma.

These results highlight that diverse odour-active volatile compounds can be produced during development of baked goods dependent on the raw material used. Therefore, the right choice of ingredient type is crucial in processing food with designed sensory attributes.

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